

Preliminary identification of anthracycline-interacting targets

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Project summary:

The **S2TOX** - “*Mechanistic Assessment of Cardiotoxicity using Integrated In Silico and In Vitro Modeling*” project is an interdisciplinary initiative designed to replace traditional animal testing with a human-relevant, *in vitro-in silico* platform for evaluating drug-induced cardiotoxicity (DICT). Using anthracyclines as a primary case study, the project aims to mechanistically explain and predict how cardiac damage varies according to a patient's sex and age.

S2TOX is structured into four Work Packages (WP):

- WP1 (*in silico* modeling): Optimizing an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) network and building a probabilistic Boolean model parameterized with human transcriptomics data.
- WP2 (*in vitro* testing): Establishing a human iPSC-derived cardiac organoid platform to generate functional and omics data for model calibration.
- WP3 (validation & trials): Validating the model against the organoid data and conducting virtual clinical trials to profile toxicity mechanisms across different patient profiles.
- WP4 (management & training): Open science dissemination, data management, and professional development.

Background

This report provides an overview of the carriers, transporters, enzymes, and targets associated with four anthracycline drugs, daunorubicin (DNR), doxorubicin (DOX), epirubicin (EPI), and idarubicin (IDA), based on data available at DrugBank (<https://www.drugbank.ca/>) (Knox et al., 2024).

DOX, DNR, EPI and IDA are cytotoxic anthracycline antibiotics. These drugs generally function as antineoplastic agents by interfering with DNA synthesis and function, often involving intercalation and topoisomerase II inhibition.

Table 1. List of gene names for the identified targets, enzymes, transporters, and carriers for daunorubicin, doxorubicin, epirubicin, and idarubicin:

Type	Molecule Name	Gene Name	Drug(s)
Target	DNA Topoisomerase 2-alpha	TOP2A	DNR, DOX, EPI, IDA
Target	DNA Topoisomerase 2-beta	TOP2B	DNR, DOX, EPI, IDA

Target	Telomerase Reverse Transcriptase	TERT	DOX
Target	Nucleolar and Coiled-body Phosphoprotein 1	NOLC1	DOX
Enzyme	Carbonyl Reductase [NADPH] 1	CBR1	DNR, DOX
Enzyme	Carbonyl Reductase [NADPH] 3	CBR3	DNR, DOX
Enzyme	Aldo-keto Reductase family 1 member B1	AKR1B1	DNR, DOX
Enzyme	Aldo-keto Reductase family 1 member C3	AKR1C3	DOX
Enzyme	Aldo-keto Reductase family 1 member A1	AKR1A1	DOX
Enzyme	Aldo-keto Reductase family 1 member C4	AKR1C4	DOX
Enzyme	Aldo-keto Reductase family 1 member B10	AKR1B10	DOX
Enzyme	Cytochrome P450 3A4	CYP3A4	DNR, DOX
Enzyme	Cytochrome P450 1B1	CYP1B1	DNR, DOX
Enzyme	Cytochrome P450 3A5	CYP3A5	DNR
Enzyme	Cytochrome P450 2D6	CYP2D6	DOX, IDA
Enzyme	Cytochrome P450 2B6	CYP2B6	DOX
Enzyme	Cytochrome P450 2C9	CYP2C9	IDA
Enzyme	NADPH-cytochrome P450 reductase	POR	DNR, DOX
Enzyme	NAD(P)H dehydrogenase [quinone] 1	NQO1	DOX
Enzyme	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 2, mitochondrial	NDUFS2	DOX
Enzyme	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 3, mitochondrial	NDUFS3	DOX
Enzyme	NADH dehydrogenase [ubiquinone] iron-sulfur protein 7, mitochondrial	NDUFS7	DOX
Enzyme	Nitric Oxide Synthase 1	NOS1	DOX
Enzyme	Nitric Oxide Synthase, inducible	NOS2	DOX
Enzyme	Nitric Oxide Synthase 3	NOS3	DOX
Enzyme	Xanthine dehydrogenase/oxidase	XDH	DOX
Enzyme	UDP-glucuronosyltransferase 2B7	UGT2B7	EPI
Enzyme	Cytosolic phospholipase A2	PLA2G4A	EPI
Transporter	ATP-dependent translocase ABCB1 (P-gp)	ABCB1	DNR, DOX
Transporter	Multidrug resistance-associated protein 1 (MRP1)	ABCC1	DNR, DOX, EPI, IDA
Transporter	Broad substrate specificity ATP-binding cassette transporter ABCG2 (BCRP)	ABCG2	DNR, DOX
Transporter	ATP-binding cassette sub-family C member 10	ABCC10	DNR, DOX
Transporter	ATP-binding cassette sub-family C member 6	ABCC6	DNR, DOX

Transporter	ATP-binding cassette sub-family C member 3	ABCC3	DOX
Transporter	Mitochondrial potassium channel ATP-binding subunit	ABCB8	DOX
Transporter	Bile salt export pump	ABCB11	DOX
Transporter	RalA-binding protein 1	RALBP1	DOX
Transporter	ATP-binding cassette sub-family C member 2	ABCC2	DOX
Transporter	Solute carrier family 22 member 16	SLC22A16	DOX
Carrier	Albumin	ALB	DOX
Interacting Gene	Retinoic acid receptor gamma	RARG	DNR, DOX
Interacting Gene	Solute carrier family 28 member 3	SLC28A3	DNR, DOX
Interacting Gene	UDP-glucuronosyltransferase 1-6	UGT1A6	DNR, DOX
Interacting Gene	Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein D0	HNRNPD	DNR
Interacting Gene	SEC14-like protein 3	SEC14L3	DNR
Interacting Gene	Inhibitor of nuclear factor kappa-B kinase subunit epsilon	IKBKE	DNR

References

Knox, C., Wilson, M., Klinger, C. M., Franklin, M., Oler, E., Wilson, A., Pon, A., Cox, J., Chin, N. E. (Lucy), Strawbridge, S. A., Garcia-Patino, M., Kruger, R., Sivakumaran, A., Sanford, S., Doshi, R., Khetarpal, N., Fatokun, O., Doucet, D., Zubkowski, A., ... Wishart, D. S. (2024). DrugBank 6.0: The DrugBank Knowledgebase for 2024. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 52(D1), D1265–D1275. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad976>